

METHODS OF DEVELOPING INDEPENDENT SPEECH IN STUTTERING CHILDREN

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Abstract

The main task of the speech development methodology is to develop the scientific and pedagogically based factors, tools and methods of speech development in pre-school education, which give the most effective results, to equip educators, pedagogues, and parents with knowledge about the methods of speech development. , is to use the most convenient methods, to arm them with knowledge on increasing the effectiveness of organizing speech training classes.

Key words: language, speech, education, upbringing, development, verbal intelligence, memory, imagination, goal, task, vocabulary, connected speech, sound side of speech, grammatical side of speech, fiction, pedagogical principles: what to teach, how much to teach, how to teach..

Along with increasing attention to all stages of the continuous education system in our republic, including its pre-school stage, the percentage of pre-school children attending pre-school educational institutions is decreasing. should be considered as part of priority research directions. After all, as we have mentioned, how effective the stages of continuous education are to a certain extent depends on the quality of preschool education: during this period, the child's worldview and imagination can be formed. Giving it the right content and direction is an urgent problem of pedagogy and educational practice.

The historically formed content of human experience is summarized in verbal form, and its description and mastering implies the participation of speech in this process. Speech opens the way for a child to all the achievements of human culture. In general, the formation of personality and all basic mental processes (reception, thinking, etc.) is also related to the development of speech in a child. The special place of speech in the mental formation of a child makes it very important to know the conditions and factors that support its development at different stages. With the development of speech, the issue of moving forces becomes important due to the fact that it occurs in the form of rapid jumps.

Determining the forces that stimulate or hinder the development of speech in children is the key to organizing pedagogical influence on this process with a clear goal in mind.

The most important stages of acquisition of speech correspond to preschool age. Based on this, special attention is currently being paid to the study of some stages in the development of speech. Scientists have realized that the pre-speech stage plays an important role and are analyzing it in detail.

In the modern concept of speech ontogeny, it is understood that the development of a child's speech, on the one hand, is determined by external influences, and on the other hand, it is characterized by a sudden occurrence, "self-initiation". Children's acquisition of passive speech and their first speech depends to a decisive extent on the following three aspects, namely, the communicative factor, which consists of emotional connections, connections during joint movement, and sound connections.

All the child's achievements in acquiring the language system include fluent speech, which is considered as a meaningful, widespread thought that provides communication. It is distinguished by its content, logic and consistency. Fluent speech is an indicator of how well the child has mastered language, it reflects the level of the child's intellectual, aesthetic, and emotional development.

- there should be a communicative approach based on the development of speech, in particular: mastering the mother tongue should be included in the activities of speech communication, educational conditions should be brought closer to natural communication conditions;
- the nature of interaction between an adult and a child in a teaching situation should be determined by the form of communication that is the leader for this child;
- it is necessary to work on the language within the framework of the structure of speech activity and taking into account all its components: exhortation-motivation, orientation-research, performance components;
- teaching speech should be based on children's independent activity in language learning and should be related to other types of children's activity.

Learning to speak well requires developing the ability to think outside the box. It helps to be an interesting storyteller with a unique train of thought. In practice, it is necessary to try to find commonalities between two unrelated objects or

concepts. For example, what is common between a table and a cat? You can still find their own continuation of winged phrases and aphorisms. For example, continue the phrase: "Our whole life - ". Shakespeare ended it with the word "play" and what options can be considered and justified?

Speech lessons help to learn the story in different forms:

"Finish the sentences" game exercises to exercise your imagination. Adult children tell children the beginning of the story (fairy tales, poems) and they end with themselves.

To develop the skills of making long sentences from familiar words, do the exercise "Make sentences". Based on his leading questions, the child must finish the sentence started by the adult: "Masha went to the forest in a basket. Why? (picking mushrooms, visiting grandmother). What is in her basket? (nothing, pies)". Children are encouraged to continue and complete the suggestion initiated by adults, based on leading questions.

"If..." game exercises with a complex mental task to analyze, model and predict the situation. The child is invited to think about what would happen if he had a magic wand in his hand, he would become invisible and the like.

A child's speech becomes figurative and expressive only when adults understand it and communicate with it logically, so training for speech development should be easy and consistent. In order to interest children, they should use available teaching methods, involve other children, and parents themselves should be actively involved.

To create favorable conditions for training, play corners and sets of toys that allow children to create games for the development of speech at home will help. It can be the best home theater with various characters and simple decorations (designer houses, tree branches, cubes). Thus, the child learns to speak well and to improvise creatively.

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